

FEATURES OF SYNTAGMATIC ASSOCIATIONS FOR STIMULI-NAMES OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UKRAINIAN AND MODERN GREEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. 500 respondents who are Ukrainian native speakers and 100 Modern Greek speakers participated in free word association test held in March and July, 2015 in Kyiv, Ukraine, and in Athens, Greece. The data were calculated as to the frequency of responses and composed a field of associations for each stimulus. The classification of associations to the word-stimuli “food products” was based on existing classifications and on the specific of the test material. In this paper, the authors discuss the syntagmatic type of associations expressed by adjectives that represent the objective characteristics of the product and form a phrase with a word-stimulus (Terekhova, 2000). They can be roughly divided into 2 groups of associating directions: features of product attributes (52 % of all syntagmatic associations in Ukrainian language (*hereinafter – UL*) and 41% in Modern Greek (*hereinafter – MGL*)) and features of stages that the product passes (UL – 41%, MGL – 48 %). Some differences in quantitative and qualitative aspects were found during the determination of associating directions within the syntagmatic type of associations: different percentage of responses in associating directions in quantitative aspect. As to the quality, the differences lay in determination of feature directions in the languages. Thus for the associative field of Modern Greek language, the reactions that characterize the form of the product have not been found at this stage yet.

Keywords: *associative field, free association test, syntagmatic associations, ways of associating, response, stimulus, types of associations.*

Петрова Галина. Характеристика синтагматичних асоціацій на стимули-назви продуктів харчування (на матеріалі української та новогрецької мов).

Анотація. У статті подано результати аналізу матеріалів вільного асоціативного експерименту: репрезентовано спробу класифікації асоціацій на стимули-назви продуктів харчування в українській та новогрецькій мовах; подано опис одного з найбільших за обсягом – синтагматичного типу асоціацій; визначено його підтипи та подальше розгалуження; виявлено загальні та специфічні риси мовної свідомості українців та греків. у межах класифікації асоціацій на позначення продуктів харчування вагомим місцем за обсягом реакцій займають синтагматичні асоціації. Під час визначення напрямів асоціювання в межах синтагматичного типу асоціацій виявлено розбіжності в кількісному та якісному аспектах. У кількісному аспекті різняться відсоткове співвідношення реакцій у напрямках асоціювання. У якісному – відмінності полягають у визначенні підгруп характеристик у різних мовах, так зокрема в асоціативному полі новогрецької мови на цьому етапі дослідження не виявлено реакцій, що є характеристиками форми продукту.

Ключові слова: *асоціативне поле, вільний асоціативний експеримент, синтагматичні асоціації, напрямок асоціювання, реакція, стимул, типи асоціацій.*

1. Introduction

Language associations have been an object of interest of philosophers, linguists, psychologists, sociologists all around the world since the birth of the science about language. No one doubts now that the role of associations in reflecting of real connections of phenomena and objects is enormous. Associations are an important condition for mental and intellectual activity.

Associations occur during human perception of reality and constitute one of the fundamental characteristics of thinking at all levels: mundane, everyday, practical, scientific, creative and artistic (Marfina). Even Sigmund Freud and his followers supposed that uncontrolled associations are symbolic or sometimes even direct projection of the inner, often unconscious contents of consciousness (Serkin). They both form and reflect the picture of the world not only of an individual but also of an ethnic group on the whole. The formation of an image of the world occurs under the influence of many factors, in particular of advertising, whose task is not only informing, but also suggesting of a certain way of thinking, that is, influencing the worldview.

Topicality of the research. The task of the impact of advertising is implemented first of all in advertising texts that convey the main semantic message, which is suggested. This directly relates to such an important aspect of a person's everyday life, as choosing of food and cooking different dishes. Thus the lexical-semantic group "food products" needs to be thoroughly studied. In this study, word association test as a psycholinguistic tool was used to identify the associative fields of the names of food products, which are key within the advertising texts.

The theoretical foundations and practical results of conducting of associative experiments are set in the writings of many well-known scientists: O. Goroshko (features of conducting of association tests), Yu. Karaulov (construction of associative dictionaries), I. Podolian (national specificity of the semantics of phytonyms), Ye. Tarasov (psycholinguistic features of advertising), T. Kovalevska (study of the specifics of the formation of the national mentality on the material of advertising vocabulary) and others. The issue of classifying associations exists as much as the theory of associations itself. It is known that the first classification was created by Plato and Aristotle. The most complete description of existing classifications was presented by O. Goroshko (2001) in her work "The Integral Model of Free Associative Experiment". Today there are classifications suggested by N. Gasitsa, W. James, K. Dolbina, G. Ebingause, A. Zalevskaya, G. Klymenko, A. Luria, G. Muller, I. Podolian, D. Terekhova, E. Thorndike, N. Ufimtseva, E. Shubin, G. Shchur, O. Kaliuta and others. The analysis of associative fields is presented in the writings of T. Nedashkivska, O. Denisovich, I. Gordiienko-Mytrofanova, N. Lyashuk, N. Galunova, D. Terekhova and others. However, the unified classification of associations has not been created yet, that means that the problem remains unsolved either in domestic or in foreign psycholinguistics.

In Greek linguistics, this branch is not so developed. Among the scientists who study the themes of psycholinguistics, one can name such scientists as F. Grigoris, R. M. Peta, D. Stasinou, M. Zafiri, F. Lekkas, K. Riku. Studies of associative fields

of the words has only begun to appear, including the work of Mikhailo Patsis “Specificity of the associative field of words in Greek language” (Patsis, 2004). The classification of associations has not been yet the subject of research of contemporary Greek scholars.

Associations obtained as a result of a free associative experiment are usually chosen as a material for classifications. The experience of conducting of such experiments is fixed in dictionaries. So, such associative dictionaries have been published in the Ukrainian language: “Dictionary of Associative Norms of the Ukrainian Language” and “Dictionary of Associative Definitions of Nouns in the Ukrainian Language” by N. Butenko (1979; 1989), “Ukrainian Associative Dictionary” by S. Martinek (2007), “Associative Dictionary of Ukrainian Advertising Vocabulary” by T. Kovalevska, H. Sologub, O. Stavchenko (2001). Also a “Slavic Associative Dictionary: Russian, Belarusian, Bulgarian, Ukrainian” edited by N. Ufimtseva, G. Cherkasova, Yu. Karaulov, Ye. Tarasov (2004) was created on the material of the Ukrainian language. Single stimuli for food products are represented in the above dictionaries, but they do not reflect the full usage of such words in the advertising. There are no such dictionaries in the Greek language, therefore, to achieve the objectives of the study, a free word association test was conducted with Ukrainians and Greeks in 2015 in the most approximate conditions.

The *purpose* of the article is to characterize the syntagmatic associations to stimuli-names of food products based on the results of a free associative experiment in Ukrainian and Modern Greek languages.

Syntagmatic associations are represented mainly by adjectives, that reflect both the objective properties of objects designated by the stimulus, and emotional-evaluative characteristics that are important for representatives of a certain ethnos in their perception. The phrases, which form associations with the stimulus, are the basis for constructing of texts, including the texts of advertising. So, a study of syntagmatic associations gives an idea of the most stable links between words in the respondents’ linguistic consciousness, of the influence of advertising on the consciousness of respondents and so on.

To achieve the purpose, the following tasks are solved: 1) associative fields of words-stimuli are formed according to the results of the experiment; 2) an attempt to make a classification of associations of words-stimuli "food products" is made up based on the experience of previous classifications; 3) subtypes, groups and subgroups of syntagmatic associations are characterized; 4) the general and distinct within the limits of syntagmatic associations in the Ukrainian and Modern Greek languages are revealed.

2. Methods

The study is based on a comparable analysis of the results of free association test conducted with the aim of studying the verbal associations of the Ukrainians and the Greeks. Quantitative and qualitative processing of associations is carried out. Food products have been chosen as words-stimuli being an essential sphere of life of

every nation. Its formation is influenced by many factors: from the personal tastes to the media and advertising as its integral part.

500 respondents who are Ukrainian native speakers (students of different branches of studying and courses of Kyiv National Linguistic University) and 100 Modern Greek speakers (students of the higher educational institutions of Athens) aged from 17 to 25 years old participated in the free associative experiment. The study was conducted between March-July 2015 in Ukraine (Kyiv) and in Greece (Athens).

Words-stimuli for food products are selected by conducting a preliminary pilot associative experiment, among them the most frequent were: АПЕЛЬСИН / ΠΟΡΤΟΚΑΛΙ (orange), ВІНО / ΚΡΑΣΙ (wine), ВІНОГРАД / ΣΤΑΦΥΛΙΑ (grapes), ВОДА / ΝΕΡΟ (water), ГАРБУЗ / ΚΑΡΠΟΥΖΙ (pumpkin), ГОРІЛКА / ΒΟΤΚΑ (vodka), ЙОГУРТ / ΓΙΑΟΥΡΤΙ (yogurt), КАВА / ΚΑΦΕΣ (coffee), ΚΑΡΤΟΠΛЯ / ΠΑΤΑΤΑ (potato), КОВБАСА / ΛΟΥΚΑΝΙΚΟ (sausage), МАСЛО / ΒΟΥΤΥΡΟ (butter), МОРОЗИВО / ΠΑΓΩΤΟ (ice-cream), М'ЯСО / ΚΡΕΑΣ (meat), ОВОЧ / ΛΑΧΑΝΙΚΟ (vegetable), ОЛИВКИ / ΕΛΙΕΣ (olives), ОЛІЯ / ΛΑΔΙ (cooking oil), ПЕЧИВО / ΜΠΙΣΚΟΤΟ (biscuit), ПИВО / ΜΠΥΡΑ (beer), РИБА / ΨΑΡΙ (fish), САЛЮ / ΛΑΡΔΙ (lard), СІК / ΧΥΜΟΣ (juice), ФРУКТ / ΦΡΟΥΤΟ (fruit), ХЛІБ / ΨΩΜΙ (bread), ЧАЙ / ΤΣΑΙ (tea), ЦОКОЛАД / ΣΟΚΟΛΑΤΑ (chocolate) and so on.

As a result of perusal of received experimental data we have calculated the frequency of responses and have composed a field of associations for each stimulus. Within the fields the ranking and quantitative perusal namely the calculation of percentage of associations for each type of classification was implemented.

On the basis of existing classifications and taking into account the specificity of the test material, an attempt to classify the associations to the words-stimuli "food products" has been made. Syntagmatic, Paradigmatic, Thematic, Phonetic, Word-building, Reminiscences (citation), Personalities, Geographical, Trademarks, National and cultural, Evaluative, Subjective (individual) associations were found in both languages.

3. Results and Discussion

In this paper, we discuss the syntagmatic type of associations (associations in which words-responses and words-stimuli form a phrase that is often agreed). As parts of this type two subtypes are allocated: 1) the syntagmatic associations that are expressed by adjectives, constitute a contracting phrase with the word-stimulus; 2) syntactic associations that are expressed by the verbs.

Syntagmatic associations that are expressed with adjectives, represent the objective characteristics of the product (Terekhova, 2000:62). They can be roughly divided into 2 groups of associating directions: characteristics of product features (52 % of all syntagmatic associations in Ukrainian language (*hereinafter* – *UL*) and 41 % in Modern Greek language (*hereinafter* – *MGL*)) and characteristics of stages that the product passes (*UL* – 41 %, *MGL* – 48 %).

Among the first group we define some subgroups.

Characteristics of outward of a product (30 % of all syntagmatic associations in UL and 23 % in MGL) (parametric spatial characteristics: size and shape characteristics, color characteristics).

In terms of **size** the products, denoted by the word-stimulus, are characterized by the reactions that are represented by the adjectives “big – small” (e.g.: АПЕЛЬСИН – *великий* (4), ОЛИВКИ – *маленькі* (1), *малі* (1)). The most frequent characteristic of this subtype was found in the associative field of Ukrainian language to the stimulus ГАРБУЗ – *великий* (23), *великий за розміром* (1). The reactions only to one stimulus were given in both languages: КОВБАСА – *длинная* (1) / ΛΟΥΚΑΝΙΚΟ – *μακρόστενο* (1).

Among the **characteristics of form** in the Ukrainian language, associations that refer to rounded forms predominate, e.g.: ВІНОГРАД – *круглий* (1), *овальний* (1). The reaction *квадратне* (1) was given to the stimulus ПЕЧИВО. These reactions have a single frequency and are situated at the periphery of the associative fields of stimuli.

The largest part of this subgroup in both languages constitute associations that denote the objective **characteristics of color** of the product, that is not only an integral feature of food products, according to which a person distinguishes them, but also can indicate the quality of the food product. The reactions to words-stimuli ВІНО / ΚΡΑΣΙ, ВІНОГРАД / ΣΤΑΦΥΛΙΑ, ГАРБУЗ / ΚΑΡΠΟΥΖΙ, М'ЯСО / ΚΡΕΑΣ, ОЛИВКИ / ΕΛΙΕΣ, ОЛІЯ / ΛΑΔΙ, ПИВО / ΜΠΥΡΑ, ФРУКТ / ΦΡΟΥΤΟ partially coincide, but the color spectrum of reactions of the Ukrainian recipients is broader than that one of the Greeks.

e.g.: ВІНО – *червоне* (76), *біле* (23), *красное* (5), *червоний* (3) / ΚΡΑΣΙ – *κόκκινο* (23), *λευκό* (12), *άσπρο* (2). According to the frequency in both languages, preference is given to red wine, that characterizes the taste preferences of the respondents of both groups. Evidently, the formation of this stereotype took place under the influence of Christian canons, where red wine symbolizes the blood of Jesus Christ, it is a metaphor for the state of communion with God.

Associations for the following stimuli are more diverse: ВІНОГРАД – *зелений* (25), *білий* (12), *синій* (6), *чорний* (2), *бузковий* (1), *салатовий* (1), *темний* (1), *фіолетовий* (1), *червоний* (1) / ΣΤΑΦΥΛΙΑ – *πράσινα* (8), *κόκκινα* (6), *λευκά* (1). Grapes is one of the most ancient solar symbol of fertility, abundance and wealth. Grape harvest festivals have been reflected in the fine arts since ancient times. The most popular images were Greek festive processions headed by Dionysus, patron god of grapevine, which represented prosperity, wealth and fun. Subsequently the excellent reputation of grapevine was strengthened by the Christian tradition that has made it an emblem of spiritual life, salvation and rebirth. That's why a grapevine is depicted on ancient Christian tombs, the frescoes of the Roman catacombs and later on church stained glass. About 150 grape varieties adapted to different soil and climate conditions have been cultivated in Greece from ancient times to the present.

Next word-stimulus has vast variety of reactions in the Ukrainian language: ГАРБУЗ – *червоний* (10), *жовтий* (7), *оранжевий* (7), *помаранчевий* (7),

зелений (3), помаранч (1) / ΚΑΡΠΟΥΖΙ – κόκκινο (3). The explanation of such a variety of associations of Ukrainian respondents is found not only in the wide use of this vegetable in cooking, but also in the feeding of domestic animals. Pumpkin has an old symbolism in Ukrainian culture, for example, to give a pumpkin to a groom means a tactful refusal in the wedding ritual of matchmaking; the phrase “relatives of a pumpkin” is used for bloodless, false relatives. As for Greece the pumpkin has been a well-known medicinal product since ancient times there. Folk and classical medicine also widely uses it nowadays. Also the pumpkin is an integral part of the cooking of the Greek nation.

Associations *М'ЯСО – червоне (9), рожеве (1), червоний (1) / ΚΡΕΑΣ – κόκκινο (3), рожеве (1)* state the natural color of qualitative food.

Reactions to stimulus *ОЛИВКИ – зелені (63), чорні (23), зелений (7), зелений колір (3), чорний (2), блакитні (1), болотний колір (1), синій колір (1) / ΕΛΙΕΣ – μαύρες (10), πράσινες (2)* are represented more variedly in Ukrainian language. Such close attention to the imported foodstuff of Ukrainians, obviously, can be explained by the desire to find out the properties of an atypical food product. For Greeks, olives are a special product. In the history of Ancient Greece, olive played the most prominent role. Firstly, the Hellenes used it for food. Secondly, three types of butter were squeezed out of olives: extra virgin oil was used for food; oil of the second grade, mixed with fragrances, used for lubrication; And rancid, inedible oil, was used to illuminate the housing. Even in the period of antiquity, olive appears to be a large and multivalued symbol. Greeks crowned the athletes-winners of the Olympic Games with olive wreaths, woven in sacred groves as a sign of victory. During the wedding ceremonies, brides emphasized their innocence and chastity, pricking olive leaves to their dresses. Thus, olives have been a truly universal product for the Greeks.

The reactions to the characteristic of color to stimuli *ЙОГУРТ, ОЛІЯ* and their correlates in the Modern Greek language were represented in both languages, but they don't coincide, for example: *ЙОГУРТ – рожевий (4), білий (1), червоний (1) / ΓΙΑΟΥΡΤΙ – πράσινο (1)*; *ОЛІЯ – жовта (9), сонячна (3) / ΛΑΔΙ – πράσινο (1)*. Differences in the color characteristics of the oil are explained by the usual stereotypes according to the idea of this food product inherent to representatives of Ukrainian and Modern Greek ethnic groups. In Ukraine, oil is initially produced mainly from sunflower, and it has a golden, yellow color, "sunny", as the respondents spate. In Greece, olive oil is the most common, it has a greenish tint. Its importance in the food system is extremely high. The culture of production and use of this product reaches far back, it is even reflected in Greek mythology. This information is often used by advertisers to create the most influential ads for the relevant consumer audience.

The second subgroup of syntagmatic associations – **the characteristics of taste peculiarities** of the product denoted by the word-stimulus has small discrepancies in the amount of reactions: UL – 21%, MGL – 18 % and further branching.

General characteristics of taste: the semantics of the “tasty” in Ukrainian language is verbalized by the lexemes “смачний, смачна, смачне, смачні” the

Russian-language lexeme “ВКУСНЫЙ” and the English-language “delicious”. Semantics of “unsavory” is verbalized by the lexemes “несмачний, несмачна, несмачне, несмачні, бридкі, огидне, огидні, гідке”. According to the analysis of the answers of the Greek-speaking population, it is verbalized by the lexemes “νόστιμος” and “άγευστος” respectively.

Corresponding reactions are presented to stimuli ВІНОГРАД, ГАРБУЗ, НЕСКАФЕ, ПЕЧИВО, СІКЕРС, ШОКОЛАД and their correlates in Modern Greek language. Some stimuli received only positive characteristics, both in Ukrainian and in Modern Greek language, e.g.: ШОКОЛАД – *смачний (13)* / ΣΟΚΟΛΑΤΑ – *νόστιμο (1)*; ВІНОГРАД – *смачний (3), смачно (3)* / ΣΤΑΦΥΛΙΑ – *νόστιμο (2)*.

Other stimuli in the Ukrainian language caused both positive and negative characteristics, reflecting the subjective taste preferences, e.g.: ГАРБУЗ – *несмачний (2), смачний (1)* (in Modern Greek language the same stimulus has only one reaction ΚΑΡΠΟΥΖΙ – *νόστιμο (4)*); КАВА – *смачна (5), несмачна (1)*; ОЛИВКИ – *смачні (16), несмачні (14), бридкі (2), огидні (1)*; ПИВО – *гідке (2), смачне (1)*; САЛЮ – *несмачне (4), смачне (2)*.

Ukrainian recipients responded only with positive reactions to stimuli АПЕЛЬСИН, ВОДА, ЙОГУРТ, КАРТОПЛЯ, КОВБАСА, МАСЛЮ, МОРОЗИВО, М'ЯСО, СІК, ФРУКТ, ХЛІБ.

Greek respondents gave corresponding positive responses to stimuli ΨΑΡΙ – *νόστιμο (2)*. Fish is an integral part of the cuisine of Greece as a maritime country, where fishing has been one of the main means of survival and still continues to be a popular work not only for subsistence, but also for earning money.

Characteristic of the type of taste in syntagmatic associations is represented by the help of adjectives “sweet, salty, bitter, sour, spicy” according to objective taste peculiarities of each product. This subgroup contains the most frequent reactions due to functionality of food products, during the consuming of which firstly the type of taste that they have is perceived.

The same association to stimuli, denoting the wine, pumpkin, ice cream, cookies, juice are presented in both languages. If the first stimulus reactions are more diverse, the others are characterized only by the word “sweet”. It can be explained either by the variety of the drink, denoted by stimulus ВІНО / ΚΡΑΣΙ, or by personal taste preferences of recipients, e.g.: ВІНО – *солодке (4), кисле (2), кислий (2), гірке (1)* / ΚΡΑΣΙ – *γλυκό (1), ζινό (1), πικρό (1)*; ПЕЧИВО – *солодке (27)* / ΜΠΙΣΚΟΤΟ – *γλυκό (20)*; МОРОЗИВО – *солодке (8)* / ΠΑΓΩΤΟ – *γλυκό (4)*.

Reactions to stimuli, indicating orange, grape, fruit and chocolate overlap in both languages. Ukrainian recipients added an indicator of the mixed taste – “*кисло-солодкий (1)*” in addition to the characteristics of “*солодкий (16), кислий (15)*” to the stimulus АПЕЛЬСИН, while Greeks gave only such reactions as ΠΟΡΤΟΚΑΛΙ – *γλυκό (3), ζινό (2)*.

Stimuli that denote the grapes in Modern Greek language had mainly uniform reactions ΣΤΑΦΥΛΙΑ – *γλυκά (4), γλυκό (2)*, in contrast to the Ukrainian language,

where there are more diverse characteristics of this stimulus: ВІНОГРАД – *солодкий* (12), *кислий* (2), *сладкий* (1). This trend continues in the associations to other stimuli, e.g.: ФРУКТ – *солодкий* (11), *кислий* (1), *кисло-солодкий* (1) / ФРОУТО – *γλυκό* (2); ШОКОЛАД – *солодкий* (10), *солодке* (5), *солодко* (3), *сладкое* (рус.) (1), *гіркий* (3), *горький* (рус.) (1) / ΣΟΚΟΛΑΤΑ – *γλυκό* (14); ОЛИВКИ – *гіркий* (1), *кислий* (1), *кислі* (1), *солоне* (1), *солоний* (1), *солоні* (1) / ΕΛΙΕΣ – *αλμυρές* (2).

The diverse reactions of Ukrainian and Greek recipients to the stimuli that denote sausage and oil are explained not only by subjectively different perceptions of taste, but also by an objectively different way of producing these products: КОВБАСА – *солоний* (1) / ΛΟΥΚΑΝΙΚΟ – *πικάντικο* (4); МАСЛЮ – *солодке* (1) / ΒΟΥΤΥΡΟ – *αυγάτο* (1).

Some stimuli had reactions only from representatives of one of the groups, that demonstrates less importance of the taste qualities of these foods for representatives of another group. The majority of such reactions belong to Ukrainian recipients, in particular to stimuli: ВОДА, ГОРІЛКА, ЙОГУРТ, КАВА, КАРТОПЛЯ, М'ЯСО, ПИВО, САЛЮ, ЧАЙ. There is only one stimulus, that has the reaction belonging to this subgroup from the Greek recipients: ΤΥΡΙ – *αλμυρό* (1). This is explained by the national specifics of popularity of salted cheese (goat cheese feta) in Greece.

Characteristics of flavor of the product, denoted by the word-stimulus (UL – 1,3%, MGL – 0,2 %) are presented by a small homogeneous subgroup of associations that express the objective characteristics according to the perception of the product by the olfactory receptors. They are expressed by synonyms “fragrant, flavored” etc. Such characteristics are more typical for Ukrainian recipients, e.g.: ХЛІБ – *запахний* (10), *ароматний* (1), *пахучий* (1); КАВА *запахна* (6), *ароматна* (1), *духмяна* (1), *пахуча* (1); ПИВО – *духмяне* (1). Only one stimulus caused such reaction of Greek recipients: ΤΣΙΧΛΑ – *μυρωδάτη* (1).

The second group has further classification.

A. **Characteristics of consumption of the product**, denoted by the word-stimulus (27 % of all syntagmatic associations in UL and 21 % in MGL) have further branching.

Characteristics of general quality of the product are the most versatile, they cover different areas of product's features, that are important for its consumption. Stimuli ВІНО, ВОДА, ГОРІЛКА, МІНЕРВА, ПАТАТА are characterized by features “good-bad”. Associations to stimuli ВІНО, ВОДА, ПАТАТА have positive connotation, e.g.: ВІНО – *добре* (1), *якісне* (1); ВОДА – *добра* (1), ПАТАТА – *πάντα ωραία* (1); ВОДА та ПОРТОКАΛΙ – neutral (ВОДА – *звичайна* (1), ПОРТОКАΛΙ – *κανονικό* (1); ГОРІЛКА – negative (ГОРІЛКА – *ποганий* (1)).

Characteristics of naturalness and freshness of the product are very important in choosing of a product, because every person tries to get the best product, the freshest and most useful one. These characteristics are verbalized by antonyms “real – not real, fresh – stale, natural – artificial”.

Some stimuli caused only positive reactions in both groups of recipients, e.g.: РИБА – *свіжа* (1) / ΨΑΡΙ – *φρέσκο* (5); СІК – *натуральний* (3), *свіжий* (2) / ΧΥΜΟΣ – *φυσικός* (1), *φρέσκος* (7); М'ЯСО – *свіже* (4), *справжнє* (1); ΣΤΑΦΥΛΙΑ – *φυσικό* (1); ΚΑΡΠΟΥΖΙ – *βιολογικό* (1). The latest reaction emphasizes the current trend to consume only organic products.

There is a specific reaction in English in the characteristics of juice, its transcribed borrowing, which has already been assimilated in Ukrainian and the Ukrainian analogue (translation): СІК – *фреш* (15), *свіжовижатий* (3), *fresh* (1), that demonstrate the global impact of English language.

The reactions of Ukrainian respondents to the stimulus КОВБАСА were both positive and negative: КОВБАСА – *несправжня* (3), *натуральна* (1), *свіжа* (1), *штучний* (1), but the fact that there were more negative responses shows the distrustful attitude of respondents towards the quality of this product. There were only negative reactions to the stimuli МАСЛО – *несвіже* (1), МОРОЗИВО – *не натуральне* (1), М'ЯСО – *гниле* (1), ГАРБУЗ – *вялий* (1), that indicates the concern of recipients as consumers of the quality of these products, the opportunity to damage health.

Characteristics of consistency of the product mainly objectively reflect their structure, they are verbalized by:

а) antonymous pairs of adjectives:

– “liquid – thick”, only in Ukrainian language (ОЛІЯ – *рідка* (5), ВОДА – *рідкий* (1), ЙОГУРТ – *рідкий* (4), *густий* (2), *рідкий у пляшці* (1));

– “soft – hard”, in both languages to the stimulus МАСЛО – *м'яке* (1) / ВОУТУРО – *μαλακό* (5); in one language to the stimuli ХЛІБ – *м'який* (8), *твердий* (1); ПЕЧИВО – *м'яке* (3); САЛО – *тверде* (1); ΨΑΡΙ – *μαλακό* (1);

– “fat – fat-free”, also in both languages, e.g.: МАСЛО – *жирне* (26) / ВОУТУРО – *άπαχο* (2); КОВБАСА – *жирна* (1) / ΛΟΥΚΑΝΙΚΟ – *παχύ* (1) etc. There are reactions only in one language: САЛО – *жирне* (19), РИБА – *жирна* (1), ТΥΡΙ – *ελαφρύ* (1).

б) adjectives “crunchy, crispy, brittle, crumbly”. Such reactions are the most frequent to the stimulus ПЕЧИВО – *хрустке* (18), *крихке* (3), *хрумке* (3), *розсипчасте* (2), that emphasizes the tastes and preferences of Ukrainian recipients. Opposite to the semantics of perception are the reaction of the Ukrainian and the Greeks to the stimulus ХЛІБ: Ukrainians pay attention primarily to the properties of the crust, and Greeks of the flesh: ХЛІБ – *крихкий* (1), *хрусткий* (1), *черствий* (1) / ΨΩΜΙ – *αφράτο* (1).

в) there are individual reactions that mark the presence of fluid in the product denoted by the stimulus, they are verbalized by adjectives “watery, juicy, diluted”, e.g.: ГАРБУЗ – *водянистий* (1), СІК – *розбавлений – 0,3 відсотки соку, все вода* (1), ФРУКТ – *соковитий* (1), АПЕЛЬСИН – *ζουμερό* (1).

Characteristics of composition of the product according to the ingredients. Such reactions are numerous in the Ukrainian language, some of them are quite frequent, e.g.: МОРОЗИВО – *шоколадне* (24), *вершкове* (7), *ванільне* (2), *бананове* (1), *карамельне* (1), *молочне* (1), *натуральне шоколадне* (1); ПИВО –

життє (2); КОВБАСА – *м'ясна* (1); МАСЛЮ – *молочне* (1). There is a reaction only to one stimulus in Modern Greek language: ΨΩΜΙ – *πολύσπορο* (1).

Characteristics of temperature of the product are expressed by antonymous adjectives “hot – cold” according to the way of its use. Most associations are given to stimuli that denote drinks. The reactions of this subgroup in both languages are presented to stimuli: ВОДА – *холодна* (6), *гарячая* (1) / ΝΕΡΟ – *κρύο* (5), *δροσερό* (5), *παγωμένο* (1); ПИВО – *холодне* (5) / ΜΠΥΡΑ – *κρύα* (4), *παγωμένη* (5), that can be explained by the use of these drinks for a sense of freshness and cooling.

Stimuli that denote tea caused mostly reactions-characteristics of high temperature, but Greeks respondents have the percentage of responses to the characteristics of low temperature that dominate, due to the culture of consumption of the drink. Ukrainians usually drink hot tea at any time of the year, but Greeks drink mostly iced tea, especially in summer and the hot tea is given only to sick person: ЧАЙ – *гарячий* (7), *холодне* (1) / ΤΣΑΙ – *ζεστό* (4), *χοτ* (1), *κρύο* (4).

Reactions to the following stimuli can also be explained by the tradition of their consumption: ГОРІЛКА – *холодна* (2), ШОКОЛАД – *гарячий* (2), ΚΡΑΣΙ – *ζεστό* (1), ΓΙΑΟΥΡΤΙ – *παγωμένο* (1).

Reactions that describe the main characteristics of ice cream are frequent enough in both languages: МОРОЗИВО – *холодне* (38), *холодний* (1) / ΠΑΓΩΤΟ – *κρύο* (4).

Associations to stimuli that denote bread and pumpkin are also mostly the same in both languages: ХЛІБ – *гаряче* (1) / ΨΩΜΙ – *ζεστό* (4); ГАРБУЗ – *холодний* (1) / ΚΑΡΠΟΥΖΙ – *δροσερό* (4).

Characteristics of process and conditions of consumption of the product denote the features of a product, that is usable, for example, as for fruit and vegetables this feature is “*ripe*”: ГАРБУЗ – *спілий* (1); ФРУКТ – *спілий* (1); ΠΟΡΤΟΚΑΛΙ – *στεμμένο (стиглий)* (1). For other products the features are as follows: ВОДА – *питна* (18), *джерельна* (3), *кип'ячена, тільки очищена, фільтрована* (1); КАВА – *міцна* (18), *кріпка* (1); ΛΑΔΙ – *μαγειρικό* (1).

B. Characteristics of the method of cooking (UL – 9 %, MGL – 16 %). This subgroup includes reactions that denote traditional for every country methods of products' cooking, e.g.: КАРТОПЛЯ – *смажена* (29), *печена* (12), *жарена* (10), *варена* (5), *жареная* (3), *запечена* (1), *парена* (1), *підсмажена* (1), *товчена* (1) / ΠΑΤΑΤΑ – *τηγανητή* (19), *ψητή* (5), *βραστή* (4), *τηγανητές* (3); ΡΙΒΑ – *смажена* (11), *солоня* (6), *жарена* (4), *в'ялена* (3), *запечена* (3), *заморожена* (1), *копчена* (1), *печена червона* (1), *тушкована* (1) / ΨΑΡΙ – *ψητό* (12), *τηγανιτό* (2). So, the traditional ways of cooking potatoes and fish in Ukraine and Greece differ, that is reflected in the associations: the majority of associations for fried products are presented in the Ukrainian language and the majority of associations for baking of these products, that is more useful for healthy nutrition, are presented in the Modern Greek language.

Making coffee is characterized by Ukrainian recipients according to the method of grains processing: КАВА – *розчинна* (16), *мелена* (5), *зварена* (2),

цільнозернова (2), заварна (1), зернова (1), зерновой (кофе) (1), while Greek recipients pay more attention to the way of making the coffee drink: ΚΑΦΕΣ (кава) – *Ελληνικός* (16), *σκέτος* (2), *Γαλλικός* (1), *διπλός* (1), *τουρκικός* (1).

Traditional Greek yogurt is made from ordinary yogurt by removing whey, so it is also called “strained yogurt”: ΓΙΑΟΥΡΤΙ – *στραγγιστό* (4). Greek yogurt is thicker, it contains more milk fat and has a creamy structure.

Traditional methods of cooking of other food products are presented in association according to preferences of Greeks: ΛΟΥΚΑΝΙΚΟ – *κрасάτο* (3), *βραστό* (1), *ψημένο* (1) (sausage is prepared with the addition of wine to a saucepan or frying pan); ΤΣΑΙ – *ανατολίτικο* (1) (tea with the addition of oriental spices).

C. Characteristics of effects of consumption of the product (UL – 3,4 %, MGL – 2,3 %) contain frequent responses, that reflects the principles of healthy lifestyles of recipients of both countries, that requires monitoring of weight, not using of harmful substances, therefore, paying special attention to caloric content, nutritional value, and nutrient content.

Associations with semantics of usefulness are predominantly represented by adjective “useful”, for example: ЙОГУРТ – *корисний* (8), ФРУКТ – *корисний* (3), РИБА – *корисна* (3), ГАРБУЗ – *корисний* (2), М’ЯСО – *полезное* (1), ОЛИВКИ – *корисні* (1), ОЛІЯ – *корисна* (1), СІК – *корисний* (1), and adjectives “necessary, required” in both languages: ВОДА – *необхідна* (1) / ΝΕΡΟ – *απαραίτητο* (3); ОЛІЯ – *потрібна* (1).

Greek recipients presented the associations, related with the utility of the product, they are expressed by the adjectives “healthy”, that is, useful for health: ΛΑΔΙ – *υγιεινό* (1) and accordingly “unhealthy”, that is useless, harmful: ΚΡΕΑΣ – *ανθυγιεινό* (1).

Ukrainian recipients are confident in harm of consumption of such beverages as ГОРІЛКА – *шкідлива* (8), *шкідливе для здоров’я* (2) and ПИВО – *шкідливе* (2) because of devastating impact of alcohol on health. Such associations to stimuli ПЕЧИВО – *шкідливе* (1) and ХЛІБ – *шкідливий* (1) are related with the risk of increase in body weight of a person with excessive consumption of these products.

Another subgroup of syntagmatic associations with characteristics “nutritional” is connected with the nutritional value of products (for example, М’ЯСО – *поживне* (3), ЙОГУРТ – *поживний* (2)), “high-calorie” (for example, ΜΑΣΛΟ – *висококалорійне* (1), ПЕЧИВО – *калорійне* (1), САЛЮ – *калорійне* (1)). These objective products’ characteristics are perceived differently by recipients, can be evaluated both positively and negatively. For example, people with a tendency to overweight avoid high-calorie foods, so this characteristic is negative for them, and consumers who try to gain weight do not shun the use of foods with high nutritional value and evaluate this characteristic positively.

Associations of Greek recipients have opposite semantics, e.g.: ΓΟΥΑΟΥΡΤΙ – *άπαχο* (4), it means that the preference is given to more useful types of products.

There are associations that describe the impact of the product on humans in both groups of recipients, e.g.: ΒΙΝΟ – *п’янке* (2); ΠΙΒΟ – *хмельне* (2); ВОДА –

освіжаюча (1), цілюща (1); ΦΡΟΥΤΟ – δροσιστικό (1); ΚΑΦΕΣ – τονοτικό (1); ΛΑΧΑΝΙΚΟ – δροσιστικό (1).

D. Characteristics of origin of the product (UL – 1,1 %, MGL – 8,3 %) also have further branching.

Place of cultivation: ОЛИВКИ – *грецькі* (1) / ΕΛΙΕΣ – *ελληνικές* (1), *σπιτικές* (2).

Common cultivation of olive trees in Greece and wide export of olives and oil cause the associations about the origin of the stimulus ОЛИВКИ among the recipients of both groups; difference lies in the predominance of characteristic “homemade” for Greeks, who usually cultivate olive trees in their gardens. That is how Ukrainian cultivate potatoes in their kitchen-gardens (КАРТОПЛЯ – *домашня* (1)), while fruits are usually imported from other countries (АПЕЛЬСИН – *екзотичний* (1), ФРУКТ – *екзотичний* (1)) and tea harvested in China and Ceylon is the most valuable (ЧАЙ – *Китайський* (1), *Цейлонський* (1)).

Place of manufacture. Recipients of both groups prefer homemade products, consider them to be more natural and useful, that’s why the reaction “homemade” is predominant in this group of characteristics, especially in the Ukrainian language, for example: ПЕЧИВО – *домашнє* (7), САЛЮ – *домашнє* (2), ЙОГУРТ – *домашній* (1), М’ЯСО – *домашнє* (1), ХЛІБ – *домашній* (1) / ΛΑΔΙ – *σπιτικό* (2); ΤΥΡΙ – *σπιτίσιο* (1), but in quantitative terms in Modern Greek language prevails the association “rural”, made in the countryside, where the majority of products in view of the agrarian economy of Greece is produced: ΛΟΥΚΑΝΙΚΟ – *χωριάτικο* (19), ΨΩΜΙ – *χωριάτικο* (4), ΓΙΑΟΥΡΤΙ – *χωριάτικο* (1). Besides the association “homemade”, there are also associations of a wide range of manufacturing locations covering the country and region, “Greek” and “Mediterranean”, to the stimuli that denote oil, for example: ΛΑΔΙ – *σπιτικό* (2), *ελληνικό* (1), *μεσογειακό* (1). It is a wellknown fact that Greek olive oil has the best quality and fame in the world that Greeks are extremely proud about.

Way of production. Associations of this type characterize products of animal origin, for example, they represent an animal from whose milk this product is made. This type of association is more characteristic for Greek recipients: ΤΥΡΙ – *κατσικίσιο* (3), *πρόβειο* (2); ΒΟΥΤΥΡΟ – *αγελαδινό* (2); ΓΙΑΟΥΡΤΙ – *πρόβειο* (1). Only the stimulus САЛЮ caused an appropriate association with the animal from which the product was obtained among Ukrainians: САЛЮ – *свине* (2).

E. Characteristics of purchasing of the product (UL – 0,4 %, MGL – 0,9 %) are divided into the characteristics of cost (e.g.: КОВБАСА – *дорога* (1), М’ЯСО – *дороге* (1)) and the characteristics of method of purchasing: (e.g.: ПИВО – *розливне* (3), ПЕЧИВО – *вагове* (1), ΝΕΡΟ – *εμφιαλωμένο* (5)).

There is a separate group of syntagmatic associations, which we after O. Leontiev, O. Shakhnarovych and D. Terekhova call **syntactic**, they are expressed by the verbs (7 % of all syntagmatic associations in UL and 10 % in MGL). We distinguish several groups among the syntactic associations. Most syntactic associations are associated with actions that indicate the process of consumption of the product, that is, expressed by the verbs “eat, drink” in the form of affirmation or

denial, in the form of the infinitive or the first person singular. It should be noted that in the Modern Greek language, the verb form of the first person singular is used as an infinitive, therefore, unlike the Ukrainian language, it is impossible to determine without context what kind of form the recipients had in mind. There are reactions in both languages to words-stimuli ВИНО, ВОДА, ГОРІЛКА, М'ЯСО, ПИВО, РИБА, ХЛІБ, ЧАЙ and their correlatives in Modern Greek language, e.g.: М'ЯСО – *їсти* (2) / ΚΡΕΑΣ – *τρώω* (1); РИБА – *їсти* (2) / ΨΑΡΙ – *τρώω* (1); ХЛІБ – *їсти* (1), *не їм* (1) / ΨΩΜΙ – *τρώω* (1); ВОДА – *питу* (21), *пить* (рос.) (2) / ΝΕΡΟ – *πίνω*, *να πιώ* (2), *ήπια σήμερα* (1); ГОРІЛКА – *не п'ю* (5), *питу* (2), *пиячити* (2), *випивати* (1) / ΒΟΤΚΑ – *δε πίνω* (1); ПИВО – (3), *питу* (1) / ΜΠΥΡΑ – *δεν πίνω* (1), *πίνω* (1); ЧАЙ – *питу* (3), *не п'ю* (1), *пить* (рос.) (1) / ΤΣΑΙ – *πίνω* (1). Only Ukrainians presented reactions to words-stimuli АПЕЛЬСИН, ВІНОГРАД, ЙОГУРТ, КАВА, КАРТОПЛЯ, КОВБАСА, ОЛИВКИ, ПЕЧИВО, САЛЮ, СІК, ФРУКТ. Reactions to stimuli ΒΟΥΤΥΡΟ, ΠΑΓΩΤΟ, ΤΥΡΙ were given by Greeks.

The desire or necessity of consumption of the product is expressed in the reactions with the verb “want” in the affirmative or negative form, e.g.: ЙОГУРТ – *хочу* (2), КОВБАСА – *хочу* (1), ПЕЧИВО – *хочу* (1), ХЛІБ – *не хочу* (1), ФРУКТ (фрукт) – *θέλω* (1). There is a lexeme in Modern Greek language that denote thirst: ВОДА – *хочу* (1) / ΝΕΡΟ – *διψάω* (3), *ξεδιψάω* (1).

Denial to use a particular product is represented in such reactions: ГОРІЛКА – *не вживаю* (1), ОЛИВКИ – *не вживаю* (1).

Some syntactic associations **describe the process of consumption of the product** denoted by a stimulus, e.g.: ВИНО – *дегукувати* (1), *смакувати* (1); МОРОЗИВО – *куштувати* (1), *ласувати* (1) / ΠΑΓΩΤΟ – *γλείφω* (2); ΒΟΥΤΥΡΟ – *λιώνει* (2), *λιώνω* (1).

The group of reactions that denote **the process of cooking of the product** constitutes a sufficiently large amount of syntactic associations. We have found such reactions in both languages only to the stimulus М'ЯСО – *випікати* (1), *жарити* (1) / ΚΡΕΑΣ – *μαγειρεύω* (2). There are reactions in Ukrainian language to the stimuli: АПЕЛЬСИН – *вижимати в сік* (1), *чавити* (1); КАРТОПЛЯ – *чистити* (8), *жарити* (4), *саджати* (3), *садити* (2), *смажити* (2), *варити* (1); КОВБАСА – *різати* (1), РИБА – *важко чистити* (1), *чистити* (1); ХЛІБ – *пекти* (1); ЧАЙ – *настояти* (1) and in Modern Greek language to the stimulus ΛΑΔΙ – *μαγειρεύω* (1).

The group that contains associations for describing **actions that are performed on the product or using a reality** denoted by a stimulus is small in amount, e.g.: ВОДА – *питу* (1), ОЛІЯ – *важко відмити* (1), САЛЮ – *уронили* (2), ΣΤΑΦΥΛΙΑ – *φέρει* (1).

4. Conclusions

Within the classification of associations for the designation of food products, syntagmatic associations occupy an important place as for the number of reactions. Such subtypes can be named here: 1) the syntagmatic associations that are expressed

by adjectives, constitute a contracting phrase with the word-stimulus, and represent the objective characteristics of the product; 2) syntactic associations that are expressed by the verbs. The first subtype can be roughly divided into 2 groups of associating directions: characteristics of product features (taste, flavor, color, outward: size, shape, color) and the characteristics of the stages, which the product passes (origin, cultivation, purchasing, cooking, consumption and effects of products' consumption). These groups include the vast number of associations as the most relevant words in the perception of words-stimuli and of realities that they denote: the product's quality is primarily determined by good appearance, taste, usefulness etc.

Some differences in quantitative and qualitative aspects were found during the determination of associating directions within the syntagmatic type of associations: different percentage of responses in associating directions in quantitative aspect. In the aspect of quality the differences lie in determination of characteristics directions in the languages. So the reactions that characterize the form of the product weren't found in the associative field of Modern Greek language.

The perspectives of further research are: characterization of syntagmatic associations on the material of English language as well as a detailed description of other types of reactions in Ukrainian, Modern Greek and English languages; the comparing of experiment data with articles of associative dictionaries to trace the dynamics of changes in the linguistic consciousness of respondents.

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